

Psychoemotional disorders in men with infertility

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Relevance: Infertile marriage is a problem on both the psychological and social spectrum in Uzbekistan, where starting a family is associated with procreation. Therefore, any problems in this area, the lack of a timely desired pregnancy lead to a state of chronic stress in the family, which is fraught with family conflicts, subsequently with the development of sexual dysfunctions, neurotic and somatic disorders (1,2,3).

Materials and research methods: To fulfill the goals and objectives set for the dissertation research, 80 men from 18 to 33 years old were examined, from partner couples who had been in infertile marriage for more than 2 years, the control group consisted of 30 practically healthy men. We divided the men, according to the nature of the infertile marriage, into 2 groups: the 1st group (main) consisted of 50 men with various fertility disorders, and the 2nd group (comparison) consisted of 30 men with normal reproductive function in whom the cause of the infertile marriage was the female factor. In addition, a control group was examined, which consisted of 30 practically healthy men, married and with children.

Research results: More than 90% of men in infertile marriages had various kinds of complaints; in the main group this figure was 98%, and in the comparison group 80%. Patients in the study groups complained of psycho-emotional disorders - 96% and 76.7%, respectively. Another common complaint among men with infertility was general weakness (82%), while in the group with the female factor of infertile marriage, general weakness bothered only 37% of patients. Headaches were noted only in 38% of cases among people in the main group, and in 27% among men in infertile marriages due to female factor infertility. There were also complaints about dysfunction of the genitourinary system, the presence of pain during urination was noted in 50% of cases, while the presence of pathological discharge from the urethra was noted in 18 (36%) patients. The presence of pain in the testicles and pelvic area was noted in 50% (34) of cases, dyschromia of the ejaculate and a change in its consistency was noted in 24% (12) of cases.

Psycho-emotional disorders in the form of neurasthenia significantly prevailed in men with infertility, while the most common complaints of a neurasthenic nature were irritability, general weakness and sleep disturbance. These complaints were observed significantly more often in the main group (90%, 82% and 62%,

respectively), while in the comparison group these figures were 50%, 36.7% and 33.3%, respectively.

weakness and sleep disturbance. Complaints such as a feeling of tension were more common among men in infertile marriages, but there was no statistical difference between the main group (30%) and the comparison group (20%).

Decreased cognitive function was more often reported in the group of men with impaired fertility (22%), while the difference in the group was 10%. It should be noted that these complaints in the studied individuals did not resolve after rest.

Dysfunction of a sexual nature occupied the main level among all clinical aspects of neurasthenia; in males, this disorder was manifested by premature ejaculation and weak erection, as well as a low level of sexual desire, in the main group it was 52%, in the comparison group 20%.

Individuals with neurasthenia also noted high sensitivity to high-pitched sounds, noise, and bright lights; these manifestations were also noted in most of the patients we studied.

Conclusions: aggravated premorbid background and psycho-emotional disorders in the form of neurasthenia significantly prevailed in men with infertility, while the most common complaints of a neurasthenic nature were irritability, general weakness and sleep problems.

Literature:

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